

BFSP, E-PAN: enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants

D2.2 Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality and characterise gene-based structural variation within pan-genomes

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

Genomic data integration and downstream analysis can be heavily influenced by variations in data quality. The specific research questions under investigation must therefore take these variations into account, and furthermore strive to eliminate them as much as possible. The goal of this effort is to differentiate the detected gene variations in pan-genomes as either technical artefacts, or biologically relevant information. But in order to do so, one must thus first be able to measure the data quality.

In this deliverable, we aimed specifically to provide multiple approaches for Quality Control (QC) of pan-genomic data, which have been implemented using different software workflow packages (Nextflow and Snakemake), and make use of different testing criteria. As QC of (pan-) genomic data can be measured on the DNA sequence level as well as the gene level, the decision was made to (at first) focus on the gene level, with a focus on gene space completeness. The generated output can, for example, be used to annotate missing genes or exclude genomes for which a minimum quality threshold has not been reached.

The generated workflows are easily extensible and can as such be modified to incorporate sequence QC checks as well. While fragmentation and quality of newly sequenced genomes is nowadays less of an issue due to the use of 4th generation sequence technologies (e.g. PacBio HIFI, Oxford Nanopore), sequence QC can still be important when including older genomic sequences. And although the E-PAN project was aimed at plant genomes, these pipelines can be applied to all kingdoms, given that the necessary reference databases are made available.

Our results on a set of 4 selected pan-genomes show that there is a wide variation of gene space completeness both between pan-genomes, and within the pan-genomes themselves.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BFSP	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens
E-PAN	Enhancing Pan-genome analysis in plants
QC	Quality Control

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Computational pipelines to assess pan-genome data quality

Pan-genome data format

While data formats for sequences and annotations are standardized (with the necessary caveats) in FASTA and GFF formats, there is currently no standard set for pan-genome data. In order to facilitate the automatic processing of pan-genomes to determine both the overall quality and the quality of individual component genomes, we have created a JSON-based data structure that incorporates both the content of the pan-genome, as well as local storage (see Figure 1). In the Git repository we have also provided several utility scripts to aid with the automatic generation of these JSON files, based on detected file structures.

```
{
  "storage": {
    "path": "/group/plaza/data/annotation/genomes/original_download/oryza_sativa/"
  },
  "pangenome": {
    "species": {
      "name": "oryza sativa",
      "tax_id": "4530"
    },
    "genomes": [
      {
        "name": "02428",
        "directory": "./02428/v1.0/",
        "cds": "02428.IGDBv1.Allset.cds.fasta",
        "gff": "02428.IGDBv1.Allset.gff",
        "proteins": "02428.IGDBv1.Allset.pros.fasta",
        "genome": "02428.genome"
      },
      {
        "name": "9311",
        "directory": "./9311/v1.0/",
        "cds": "9311.IGDBv1.Allset.cds.fasta",
        "gff": "9311.IGDBv1.Allset.gff",
        "proteins": "9311.IGDBv1.Allset.pros.fasta",
        "genome": "9311.genome"
      },
      {
        "name": "Basmati1",
        "directory": "./Basmati1/v1.0/",
        "cds": "Basmati1.IGDBv1.Allset.cds.fasta",
        "gff": "Basmati1.IGDBv1.Allset.gff",
        "proteins": "Basmati1.IGDBv1.Allset.pros.fasta",
        "genome": "Basmati1.genome"
      },
      {
        "name": "CG14",
        "directory": "./CG14/v1.0/",
        "cds": "CG14.IGDBv1.Allset.cds.fasta",
        "gff": "CG14.IGDBv1.Allset.gff",
        "proteins": "CG14.IGDBv1.Allset.pros.fasta",
        "genome": "CG14.genome"
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

Figure 1: Proposed JSON data exchange format for pan-genomic data

Standardized gene completeness measurements

Over the years, there have been multiple approaches to assess the completeness of newly sequenced and annotated genomes. One approach uses a predefined, lineage-dependent set of single-copy orthologs that are supposed to be present in all species, as a proxy for the quality and completeness of the entire genome. This BUSCO (Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs) is widely used ([Simao et al., 2015](#)), but suffers from the drawback that artificial datasets composed solely of the genes present in the BUSCO datasets can still have maximal scores. To account for this shortcoming, OMArk has been developed by the group behind the OMA database ([Nevers et al., 2025](#)), using phylogenetically delineated sets of orthologs as reference for the expected gene space complexity. Utilizing both methods and providing the summarized output to the end-user, allows for a first initial assessment of the gene space completeness status within the analyzed pan-genome.

Gene annotation transfer as a proxy for gene completeness QC

While BUSCO and OMArk can produce a very good assessment for strongly conserved orthologs, their methodology becomes less useful when considering genes that are species-/genus-specific, but not present in all genotypes of the pan-genome (see Figure 2). Here the issue lies predominantly with the softcore and accessory genes: are the genes missed in the annotations, have they become pseudogenes, or is it a real biological phenomenon. The QC analysis of these genes can be very important, for example when examining and scanning multiple cultivars for certain disease-resistant genes.

Figure 2. Gene family conservation upset plot between 8 different *Arabidopsis thaliana* cultivars. Black indicates core gene families. Grey indicates softcore gene families (i.e. families conserved in all but one cultivar). Red indicates accessory gene families (i.e. families that are present in more than one cultivar, but not in all). Green indicates cultivar-specific gene families. Image generated with an *Arabidopsis thaliana* pan-genome FRINGE instance.

Therefore, we implemented an additional QC measurement based on Liftoff ([Shumate et al., 2021](#)) by transferring gene annotations between entries of the pan-genome, and comparing them with the original gene annotation. For example, for *Arabidopsis thaliana* the cultivar COL-0 (Columbia) is the cultivar most-widely used, and the annotation of this cultivar is of higher quality than the annotations of the other cultivars, due to years of manual curation. Thus, by transferring the annotation of COL-0 to AN1, and comparing this to the existing annotation of AN1, we can see whether any species- or genus-specific genes have been missed, that were not included in the BUSCO or OMark analyses. Of course, *Arabidopsis* is an exception in the sense that the COL-0 cultivar is exceptionally well studied and annotated, and no such 'default' cultivar might be available for other pan-genomes. Therefore, we have also implemented methodologies to transfer annotations between the most 'distantly' related genomes within a pan-genome, thus maximizing the odds of recovering missed genes (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Heatmap representing pairwise Mash distance between assemblies from pan-genome *O. sativa*.

QC comparison multiple pan-genomes

One aspect that is still under investigation, is the QC comparison between multiple pan-genomes in order to set recommended thresholds for different clades. As is to be expected, testing our workflows on different pan-genomes have revealed quite some variation in QC (see next section). The question thus becomes: is this QC value 'good' or 'bad'? In order to make confident recommendations, we'd need to process as many pan-genomes as possible, which is outside the scope of this project. However, this is still something that we plan to continue working on in the coming months.

Test cases for QC analysis

We have tested our QC workflow on multiple pan-genomes, indicating the feasibility and scalability of our novel methodology. While BUSCO and OMArk are already well established, it nevertheless is important to benchmark them as well.

We can show that our novel transfer-based QC approach indicates that there is not that much benefit to be had in some species (such as *Arabidopsis thaliana*), while at the same time for other species (such as *Brassica napus*) the number of potentially missed gene annotations is pretty staggering (see Figure 4). However, while we have made additional efforts to filter out possible pseudo-genes from the transferred annotations, there is still additional work to be done to confirm that the genes that are marked as possibly not annotated, are correct.

Figure 4. Liftoff-based QC analysis for *Arabidopsis thaliana* (using COL-0 as reference) and *Brassica napus* (using Darmor as reference).

Outcomes and expected impact

Generating a stable, portable, and extensible system for QC of pan-genomes, which can be easily integrated in existing and future projects, is the main outcome. While we do not expect an immediate impact, as these genome projects are often multi-year

endeavors, we do hope that the use of our methodology - and especially our novel annotation-transfer based QC pipeline - will find their way in new pan-genome projects.

Dissemination Plans

The computational pipelines, utility scripts, and documentation will be made available and accessible on GitHub (<https://github.com/VIB-PSB>), using the MIT license.

References

Simao F., Waterhouse R., Ioannidis P., Kriventseva E., Zdobnov E. - BUSCO: assessing genome assembly and annotation completeness with single-copy orthologs. *Bioinformatics* 2015

Nevers Y., Vesztröcy A., Rossier V., Train C., Altenhoff A., Dessimoz C., Glover N. - Quality assessment of gene repertoire annotations with OMArk. *Nature biotechnology* 2025

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